

experiment was carried out in the Jayakwadi Command Area during kharif (Jul-Nov) 1984 at MAU. The dominant weeds were *Acalypha indica*, *Dinebra retroflexa*, *Corchorus aestuans*, *Digera arvensis*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Alysicarpus rugosus*, *Abutilon indicum*, and *Cyperus rotundus*.

Maximum grain yield (2.2 t/ha) was recorded with pendimethalin at 0.75 kg ai/ha supplemented with one hand

weeding at 6 wk after sowing (WAS). Grain yield was significantly superior to those with one hand weeding at 6 WAS and butachlor and thiobencarb application at 1.50 kg ai/ha. One hand weeding at 6 WAS, and applying butachlor and thiobencarb each at 1.50 kg ai/ha proved ineffective in controlling weeds in upland irrigated rice. Among the herbicides, pendimethalin was the most effective in

increasing grain yield, followed by oxadiazon (see table).

Economic analysis indicates that weeding and hoeing done twice at 3 and 6 WAS gave the highest profit. The price of pendimethalin is not available, but yields were higher than with the recommended cultural practice. When labor is short, preemergence application of pendimethalin at 1 kg ai/ha can be done, provided it is economical. *J*

Pest Control and Management

OTHER PESTS

A new virulent strain of rice root-knot nematode from Agartala, India

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Root-knot nematodes are considered severe pests of upland rice. We surveyed rice nematodes in eastern India and found rice plants heavily infested with *Meloidogyne graminicola* in Agartala. These showed bigger galls on roots compared to those produced in Cuttack and Kerala. To know whether the Agartala population is different from the Cuttack and Kerala populations, a pot experiment was carried out. The three populations were inoculated into 5 rice varieties planted in 200 ml sterilized soil at 200 larvae/pot. Egg mass counts were taken after the first generation (21 d after inoculation) and compared (see table). The Agartala isolate reproduced equally well in all the five varieties while

Rice root-nematode egg masses (transformed values) 21 d after inoculation, India.

Variety	Egg masses (no.) from		
	Cuttack	Agartala	Kerala
Annapurna	4.88	4.05	6.52
Parijat	4.95	6.57	4.13
IR36	2.40	4.97	2.36
MW10	1.47	3.33	1.39
CR190	2.37	4.54	2.09
CD at 5%	1.20	ns	1.06
at 1%	1.71	ns	1.50

the two other isolates differed significantly in their reproduction. CR190, MW10, and IR36 were rated resistant to Cuttack and Kerala isolates while Annapurna and Parijat were susceptible. The Agartala isolate is considered as a new biotype for all the five varieties found susceptible to it. *J*

Plant nematodes in rice fields

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We surveyed 3 districts in Tamil Nadu, India (South Arcot, North Arcot, and Chingleput), for the occurrence of rice phytonema. We covered a total of 110 blocks: 28 in Chingleput, and 36 in each of the 2 other districts. The reported genera in the rice rhizosphere were *Hirschmanniella*, *Tylenchorhynchus*, *Helicotylenchus*, *Criconemoides*, and *Hoplolaimus* spp. Their relative proportion in the soil and roots are

Proportion of different nematode genera in the soil and mts of rice.

Genus	Proportion in soil (%)	Proportion in roots (%)
<i>Hirschmanniella</i>	72.2	93.3
<i>Tylenchorhynchus</i>	17.9	5.4
<i>Helicotylenchus</i>	7.2	1.3
<i>Criconemoides</i>	2.0	—
<i>Hoplolaimus</i>	0.7	—

given in the table.

The predominant nematode is *Hirschmanniella* sp. which is found in both soil and roots. *Criconemoides* and *Hoplolaimus* spp. were not recovered from the roots. They occur in small proportion and were not economically important. *J*

Efficacy of nets to prevent bird damage to rice

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Nylon nets were placed over three rice varieties to determine their effectiveness against bird damage during the 1985 dry season.

Bird damage percentage in traditional varieties. Masapang, Victoria, Philippines, 1985 DS. * = significant difference between treatments 1 P = 0.05.

Two nets, 561 m² each with 36-cm² mesh, were supported 2.5 m above ground level by bamboo stakes at Masapang, Victoria, Philippines. The nets were positioned in such a way that they completely covered the plants within each plot.

Treatments involved the Binato, Utri Rajapan, and Bigas Pula varieties with four replications. Similar varieties without a net served as the control. Plots were assessed before and after the nets were set up to determine the extent of bird damage. Beginning 94 d after

transplanting nets were kept in place for 9 d over Utri Rajapan and Binato, and 17 d over Bigas Pula.

Bird damage was assessed by counting the total number of damaged and undamaged panicles from 10 randomly selected hills per plot (21 m²). In addition to the random samples, three to four hills from the borders of each plot were sampled because we observed that birds preferentially attack the border plants.

Bigas Pula and Utri Rajapan plots without a net sustained significantly

more bird damage, compared to those with a net. However, no difference was found for Binato because bird damage occurred before the net was installed. It is also likely that this variety sustained more damage because it was located at the outermost portion of the experimental field making it more susceptible to bird attack.

Although this is a preliminary test, our results show that nets may be a satisfactory solution to the problem of bird damage, especially in plots where maximum protection is needed. *ℒ*

Soil and Crop Management

Effects of pyrite used as farmer on normal soils

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Pyrite is generally used to normalize saline-alkali soils.

During 1980-81, some farmers who casually applied pyrite as a topdressing obtained surprisingly good results. They contacted us to verify the relevance of pyrite application and the appropriate application rates. A trial under normal soil achieved positive results and a detailed experiment was undertaken.

Variety Sarjoo 52 was grown in a split-plot design with three replications. Soil texture was silty loam with 7.6 pH, 0.82% organic matter, 17.6 kg available P, and CEC 24.8 meq 100 g of soil. Chemical composition of the pyrite used was 22.3% S, 20.5% Fe, 0.58% MgO, 0.13% CaO, 6.8% Al, 36.8% Si, 2.72% C, 200 ppm Zn, 500 ppm CuO, and 122 ppm Mn.

Four levels of ground pyrite — 200 kg, 400 kg, and 600 kg, and no pyrite (control) were tested at 3 fertility levels — 60-13.6-24, 80-18-32, and 120-27.248 kg NPK/ha. All P and K and half N were applied basally; the remaining N was applied in two equal installments at tillering and panicle initiation.

Table 1. Effect of pyrite levels at different fertility levels on grain yield of rice. Faizabad, U. P., India.

Fertility level (kg NPK/ha)	Yield (t/ha) at pyrite level of				Mean yield (t/ha)
	0	200 kg	400 kg	600 kg	
Low (60-13.6-24)	2.7	2.7	2.9	3.3	2.9
Medium (80-18.0-32)	2.9	3.0	3.3	3.6	3.2
High (120-27.2-48)	3.5	3.8	3.9	3.9	3.8
Mean	3.0	3.2 (1.51)	3.4 (3.32)	3.6 (5.73)	
Fertility combination CD at 5%	0.1		pyrite 0.2	Interaction ns	

Table 2. Grain yield and ancillary characters as affected by pyrite topdressing at different fertility levels. Faizabad, U. P., India, 1984-85.

Treatments	Panicles/ linear m	Wt/panicle (g)	Grains/ panicle	1000- grain wt (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Fertility levels (kg NPK/ha)					
Low (60-13.6-24)	48	2.89	114	22.3	2.9
Medium (80-18-32)	50	2.95	118	22.4	3.2
High (120-27.2-48)	53	2.89	124	22.5	3.8
CD at 5%	—	—	5	—	1.4
Pyrite doses (kg/ha)					
0	47	2.80	115	22.4	3.0
200	49	2.85	117	22.4	3.2
400	51	2.91	119	22.3	3.4
600	55	3.08	121	22.4	3.6
CD at 5%	—	0.14	—	—	1.7

The pyrite was topdressed 20 d after transplanting. The crop was irrigated as needed.

Grain yields increased at all application levels up to 600 kg/ha (Table 1). Response was highest at medium fertility.

The yield increase was due to

increased panicle weight (Table 2). Although the data did not show significant increases in panicle numbers per linear m or grain numbers per panicle, both characters increased with pyrite applications.

That pyrite is rich in S, Fe, and Si and has traces of Zn and Mn might be